

ECOMELIORATIVE ASPECTS OF USING ARZIQ SOILS OF CENTRAL FERGANA

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Abstract: The article analyzes the ecomeliorative changes in the irrigated soils of Central Fergana, specifically focusing on *arziq* (cemented gypsiferous) and sandy massifs over a long period of cultivation. The study substantiates that while meliorative measures have been effective in homogeneous non-*arziq* meadow-saz soils, where a desalinization process is observed, the situation is different in *arziq* and sandy soils. Specifically, it was determined that salt leaching is difficult in soils containing dense, compacted *arziq* layers with large amounts of gypsum (1-66%) and carbonates (3-16%), as well as in sandy areas with multi-layered lithological structures. The author scientifically concludes that based on the water-physical properties of these "problematic" soils, it is necessary to develop a system of new approaches and measures distinct from standard methods to improve their meliorative state.

Keywords: Central Fergana, *arziq* soils, ecomeliorative state, sandy tracts, gypsiferous layer, soil salinization, lithological structure, meadow-saz soils.

Introduction: The soils formed in Central Fergana were mainly developed in the 1950s. During the periods of development and subsequent use, a series of measures were applied regarding their melioration and fertility enhancement, and these works are still being implemented today. These measures have relatively stabilized the ecological environment of the regional hydromorphic non-*arziq* soil profile; however, in the profile of *arziq* soils, the amount of water-soluble salts remains high, and the ecomeliorative state of the soils is unsatisfactory.

Characteristics of Arziq Soils: The accumulation and alteration of salts in these soils depend on the geomorphological location of the territory and the degree of anthropogenic influence. *Arziq* soils possess a unique profile structure with dense and weakly water-permeable heterogeneous *arziq* layers. These layers, which have

developed and formed over long periods, possess very large reserves of gypsum (1-66%) and carbonates (3-16% CO₂).

The *arziq* layers have extremely dense compaction and poor water permeability. Therefore, dry residue is accumulated to a high degree in the *arziq* and supra-*arziq* layers, reaching 0.9-1.2% along the profile. The supra-*arziq* layers are moderately saline according to the amount of dry residue. The distribution of the amount of all salts along the profile is distributed similarly to the dry residue. Among anions, sulfates (0.2-0.8%) predominate, and among cations, calcium content (0.2%) predominates. Data from V. Isaqov, who conducted research here in 1978, also showed that the meliorative state of these soils at that time depicted almost the current state.

Comparison with Non-Arziq Meadow Saz Soils: The profile of non-*arziq* meadow saz soils distributed in the territory differs from *arziq* soils by almost all morphological characteristics, as well as salt quantity and composition. These soils have loose compaction and good water permeability. There are no extremely hard and compacted layers. In the profile of these soils, the amount of carbonates is around 6-8%, and gypsum is 10-14%. Salts washing down from the top to the bottom under the influence of irrigation and precipitation waters do not accumulate in any single layer, and their continuous leaching occurs. As a result, it was determined that the amount of dry residue in them is low (0.4-0.6%), and all cations and anions gradually increase along the profile from top to bottom.

Ecological Conditions of Sandy Tracts

The most complex, heaviest ecological and meliorative conditions in the Fergana Valley are also characteristic of sandy tracts.

1. On one hand, deflation, blowing, and drifting processes constantly exert a negative influence on farming in this area and its surrounding lands.
2. Secondly, the layered arrangement of extremely dense and cemented gypsum, *arziq*, *shokh*, and solonchak layers in the profile of soils formed in this area determines the unsatisfactory water-physical properties of the soils.
3. Thirdly, the agronomic and meliorative indicators of 20-150 cm shifted and deposited sand layers formed on top of soils as a result of land leveling works are poor.

According to what has been stated, the efficiency of irrigation, agro-, and hydromeliorative measures is very low.

Changes in Sandy Soil Salinity: The soils of sandy tracts also began to be developed from the 50s of the last century. Serious changes occurred in the composition and amount of water-soluble salts in the developed soils. The amount of water-soluble salts in the soil profile decreased relatively across the entire region. The chemistry of salinization shifted from the chloride-sulfate type to the sulfate type. *Arziq* solonchaks shifted to the *arziq* solonchak-like type, but the decrease in salt quantity in their profile is very small; while the total amount of salts was almost preserved (0.5-2.3%), a redistribution along the profile occurred. In the composition of salts, the amount of chlorides (0.009-0.033) and sodium (0.008-0.047) decreased, the change in sulfate quantity was very small (0.35-1.3%), and the high value of toxic salts (0.03%) was preserved due to alkali.

Layers consisting of deposited sands are distinguished by the lowest amount of salts in their composition. In deposited sandy soils, the highest amount of salts (2.3%) has shifted to the middle part of the soil profile. Salts present in the extremely dense, strongly cemented *arziq* layers located in the middle part of the soil profile have remained almost unchanged in both quantity and composition during 25-30 years of irrigation.

Conclusion: Thus, meadow saz soils in Central Fergana, which have a profile that is homogeneous in mechanical composition and a relatively loose structure, have passed into the desalinization stage or are on the verge of it as a result of various current measures being applied; maintaining their moderate ecomeliorative state is required. However, in *arziq* soils with light mechanical composition of sandy tracts and soils with relatively heavy mechanical composition possessing extremely dense compacted layers such as *berch*, *shokh*, *arziq*, and gypsum, and having a profile with multi-layered mechanical composition, salinity is currently still at medium and strong levels. This necessitates the development of new systems of measures regarding the improvement of their ecomeliorative state.

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